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 Sample Name: Proszki

C_Si 8_2 M

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 10.57 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Error %
C K	81.2	0.04	90.1	6.9
O K	2.7	0.03	2.3	8.3
Si K	16.1	0.05	7.6	5.6

/Lukasiewicz 25.02.25/Proszki/C_Si 8_2 M/Full Area 1/

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35.6 Live Time(s): 299.7 Amp Time(μs): 0.96 Resolution:(eV) 131.6

Det: Element-C2B